

NOTES

Synthesis, Magnetic and Spectral Studies of some Novel Mixed-ligand Chelates of Cobalt(II) involving β -Diketone or β -Diketoesters along with 5,7-Diiodo-8-hydroxyquinolinesulphonamides or 2,3-Dimethyl-1-(4-methylphenyl)-3-pyrazoline-5-one

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β -Diketone and β -diketoesters exhibit keto-enol tautomerism. They react with metal cations to form chelates¹, which behave as Lewis acids and form adducts with Lewis bases². As the chelates of β -diketoesters resemble to those of β -diketone, a study of the reaction of diaquabis(acetylacetonato)-, diaquabis(methylacetoacetato)- and diaquabis(ethylacetoacetato)cobalt(II) with 5,7-diiodo-8-hydroxyquinoline-4-(*m*-methoxybenzene)sulphonamide (DIHQMBS), 5,7-diiodo-8-hydroxyquinoline-4-(*m*-ethoxybenzene)sulphonamide (DIHQEBS) and 2,3-dimethyl-1-(4-methylphenyl)-3-pyrazolin-5-one (DMMPHP) was undertaken on account of biological importance³ of these organic compounds.

Experimental

Commercially available A.R. grade chemicals were used for the synthesis. The ligands DIHQMBS and DIHQEBS were prepared by the method reported by Tiwari and Mishra⁴. The parent compounds diaquabis(acetyl/methyl/ethylacetoacetate) cobalt(II) were prepared by the reported method⁵ and their purity was checked by determination of decomposition temperatures.

Synthesis of complexes: Stoichiometric amount of DIHQMBS/DIHQEBS (0.01 mol) or DMMPHP (0.02 mol) dissolved in minimum volume of ethanol was added to the corresponding solution of [Co(AA)₂(H₂O)₂]/[Co(MEAA)₂(H₂O)₂]/[Co(ETAA)₂(H₂O)₂] (0.01 mol) in ethanol and the resulting solution was refluxed for 5–6 h over a hot plate at 80°. The resulting solid was washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over silica gel at room temperature

C, H and N were determined microanalytically. Cobalt was determined as CoSO₄. Sulphur was determined by treating the aqueous suspension of the chelates with Br₂-water and heating on a water-bath for complete oxidation followed by treatment with BaCl₂ in dilute HCl medium.

The magnetic susceptibility was measured on a powdered sample using a Gouy balance. Molar conductance was measured in DMF using 10⁻³ M solution. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 8-100 spectrophotometer and ir spectra (nujol) on a Perkin-Elmer 457 spectrophotometer.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE CHELATES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Colour	Decom. temp. °C
		Co	N	S		
1.	[Co(AA) ₂ (DIHQEBS)]	6.76 (6.91)	3.39 (3.28)	3.50 (3.75)	Dark brown	>310
2.	[Co(MEAA) ₂ (DIHQEBS)]	6.42 (6.66)	3.26 (3.16)	3.49 (3.61)	Dark brown	>315
3.	[Co(ETAA) ₂ (DIHQEBS)]	6.57 (6.46)	3.25 (3.06)	3.70 (3.50)	Dark brown	>310
4.	[Co(AA) ₂ (DIHQMBS)]	7.28 (7.03)	3.18 (3.33)	3.68 (3.81)	Brown	>320
5.	[Co(MEAA) ₂ (DIHQMBS)]	6.49 (6.77)	3.34 (3.21)	3.50 (3.67)	Brown	>325
6.	[Co(ETAA) ₂ (DIHQMBS)]	6.38 (6.56)	3.24 (3.11)	3.43 (3.56)	Brown	>330
7.	[Co(AA) ₂ (DMMPHP) ₂]	8.70 (8.92)	8.60 (8.47)	—	Light blue	>310
8.	[Co(MEAA) ₂ (DMMPHP) ₂]	8.39 (8.51)	8.21 (8.08)	—	Light blue	>310
9.	[Co(ETAA) ₂ (DMMPHP) ₂]	8.30 (8.18)	7.91 (7.76)	—	Light blue	>310

Results and Discussion

The ir spectra of the parent compounds show the presence of coordinated water molecules as revealed by a band for ν_{OH} at $3440-3450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ while the chelates do not show absorption in this region. This shows the replacement of water molecule by the reacting ligands. The significant bands due to coordinated β -diketone and β -diketoesters are observed at $1590-1605\text{ (C=O)}$ and $1495-1510\text{ cm}^{-1}\text{ (C=C)}$ ⁶, respectively, in all the chelates.

Ligands, DIHQEBS and DIHQMBS possess two potential donor sites—quinoline ring nitrogen and hydroxyl oxygen. A broad band at $3250-3350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in DIHQEBS and DIHQMBS has been assigned to ν_{OH} . The appearance of this band in the chelates sl. nos. 1-6 (Table 1) indicates non-deprotonation of OH group in these ligands. The significant absorption bands due to coordinated DIHQEBS and DIHQMBS are observed at $1620-1630\text{ (C=N)}$ and $1105-1110\text{ cm}^{-1}\text{ (C-O)}$ in the complexes sl. nos. 1-6, which are in agreement with the reported result⁷. These results show that DIHQEBS and DIHQMBS behave as neutral bidentate ligands. The ligand DMMPHP possesses only the cyclic carbonyl oxygen as a donor site. The comparison of the ir spectral bands of the free ligand and its derivatives shows that the band at $1668\text{ cm}^{-1}\text{ (CO)}$ in the free DMMPHP is shifted to lower wave-numbers in the chelates and appears at $1570, 1565$ and 1568 , respectively, in the complexes sl. nos. 7-9 (Table 1). This concludes the bonding of the cyclic carbonyl oxygen⁸ to cobalt.

Low molar conductances ($10.68-18.52\ \Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$) of the chelates indicate their non-electrolytic nature. The values of magnetic moment of these chelates lie in the range of $4.90-5.10\text{ B.M.}$ ⁹ suggesting the presence of three unpaired electrons, and hence the chelates are spin-free with octahedral stereochemistry. All the chelates exhibit two absorption bands at $8990-9800$ and $17500-20400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$) and an intense band at $35200-36500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (absorption of ligand molecules) as observed for octahedral bis-chelates of the metal acetylacetonates¹⁰. Thus it is reasonable to proposed octahedral structure to the synthesised compounds.

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